

Liquid Crystalline Characteristics of Ester Mesogens. *p*-Chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates

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The newly synthesised homologous series *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates (1) can be compared with the series *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene *p*'-chloroanilines¹ (2). All the homologues of series 2 are mesogens whereas in the series 1, the first two members are non-mesogens. In series 2 the first four members decompose at high temperatures. With decrease in length of the molecules of series 1 than that of series 2, the overall transition also decreases by about 150°. Series 2 homologues are nematogens upto the tenth carbon; from the twelfth member onwards only smectic mesophase is exhibited. In series 1 the nematic mesophase appears from the third member and continues upto the sixth member; from seventh member the homologues are pure smectogens. The N-I and S-I transition curves of series 1 show rising tendency - a criterion of low melting series, while in series 2 a falling tendency is shown which is indicative of high melting character. In series 2 the odd-even effect is unusually absent as against the usual alternating effect shown by series 1. From texture viewpoint both the series have common features; the nematic mesophase is threaded when it is the only phase shown and homeotropic within poly mesomorphic region, whereas the smectic mesophase is focal conic fan shaped of smectic-A variety. In general series 1 is more smectogenic than series 2.

SEVERAL homologous series of compounds have been found to exhibit mesomorphism whose existence has been attributed to their molecular geometry and play of molecular forces arising therefrom. We have studied some homologous series with ester and azomethine linkages as central bridges besides two or more benzene rings^{2,3}. We also have studied a series with ester linkage as the central bridge and NO₂ group as one of the terminal groups⁴. Quite a good number of homologous series with halogens as terminal groups are reported in literature⁵⁻⁹. Continuing our search in this field we have also synthesised a homologous series of ester mesogens with chloro group as the terminal substituent and vinylcarboxy as the central bridge, viz. *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates. The variations obtained in the liquid crystalline characteristics of this newly synthesised homologous series are compared with the earlier presented series, viz. *p*-(*p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene *p*'-chloroanilines¹.

Experimental

Preparation of the homologues: *p*-*n*-Alkoxybenzaldehydes, *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamic acids, and *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyl chlorides were prepared by the reported methods^{10,11,2}. The esters *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates were synthesised by warming the mixture of *trans-p*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyl chlorides (0.015 mol) with *p*-chlorophenol (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (10.0 ml) for 1 h and then allowed to stand overnight. After

distilling the excess SOCl₂, it was acidified with cold dilute HCl and the resulting precipitated products were washed with water and NaOH and purified with column chromatography and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

TABLE 1—HOMOLOGOUS SERIES *p*-CHLOROPHENYL
p'-*n*-ALKOXYCINNAMATES

No. of C atoms in alkyl chain n	Transition temperatures °C					
	Cr	.	S _A	.	N	I
1	.	—	.	—	.	196.5
2	.	—	.	—	.	195.0
3	.	—	.	106.5	.	118.5
4	.	98.5	.	108.0	.	122.0
5	.	87.5	.	114.0	.	117.5
6	.	87.0	.	118.0	.	124.0
7	.	79.5	.	—	.	119.5
8	.	81.0	.	—	.	122.0
10	.	78.0	.	—	.	123.0
12	.	87.0	.	—	.	120.0
14	.	88.0	.	—	.	117.0
16	.	89.5	.	—	.	114.5
18	.	87.5	.	—	.	106.5

Method of study: The transitions and other characteristics were studied using a Kofler heating stage polarising microscope.

Results and Discussion

The homologous series *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-*n*-alkoxycinnamates (1) is a low-melting series since

the N-I transitions show a clear, though slight, rising tendency as the series is ascended^{1,2} (Fig. 1). The first two members are non-mesogens (Table 1). The Cr-M or Cr-I transition curve falls a little bit from the first to the second member followed by a relatively steeper fall at the third homologue on

Fig. 1. *p*-Chlorophenyl *p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamates: (●) solid-mesomorphic, (○) nematic-isotropic, (Δ) smectic-nematic, and (⊗) smectic-isotropic.

account of which the third member exhibits a mesophase of about 6°. Thereafter the Cr-M curve shows more or less a gradual fall upto the tenth homologue. From tenth to the dodecyloxy member the Cr-M curve rises somewhat ending into a plateau like levelling-off effect at the octadecyloxy member. The N-I transition curve shows alternating effect upto the sixth homologue; from seventh homologue only smectic phase persists. It seems that the terminal attractions are not sufficient enough to resist a thermal breakdown process and adopt nematic orientation in the first two members until the alkoxy group at the third homologue gains sufficient length-to-breadth ratio, so as to cause lowering of transitions and adopt mesomorphic nematic orientation. Polymesomorphism is exhibited between the fourth and sixth members; the seventh and onward members are pure smectogenic in nature. The S-N curve rises steeply forming an arc and the smectic mesophase length is enhanced at the cost of nematic phase as the alkyl chain length increases. This homologous series is more smectogenic than nematogenic; the S-I curve shows a gradual rise reaching the maximum at the tenth derivative. The lower N-I curve shows continuity with the S-I curve; even the S-N curve seems to be merging with the lower N-I and S-I curves at the seventh homologue. The more smectogenic nature of the series concludes that the lateral forces have predominance over the terminal attractions. Extrapolation of the two N-I curves indicates 110° and 117° as the latent I-N transitions for the first and second members respectively, which could have been realisable had the Cr-I transitions of these members been not high. Similar extrapolation of the S-N curve to the left indicates probable latent N-S transitions for the third and

second members at 82° and 50° respectively, which are also not realisable on account of the high crystallising tendency of these homologues. The texture of the nematic phase is threaded where it is the only mesophase shown; however, it is homeotropic in the polymesomorphic region. The smectic phase shows focal conic fan shaped texture of smectic-A variety.

This newly synthesised homologous series 1 can be compared with the earlier presented series, *p*-(*p'*-*n*-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene *p''*-chloroanilines (2)¹. The first two members in the series 1 are non-mesogens, whereas in series 2 all the homologues are mesogens (Fig. 2). The series 2 homologues with one more benzene ring and central linkage, -CH=N-, show high transitions as compared to

Fig. 2. *p*-(*p'*-*n*-Alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzylidene *p''*-chloroanilines: (●) solid-mesomorphic, solid-isophoric, (○) nematic-isotropic, (Δ) smectic-nematic and (⊗) smectic-isotropic; (×) decomposition point.

those of the series 1; even the first four members of the series 2 decompose at high temperatures without passing into isotropic phase. The series 2 shows polymesomorphism between the fourth and tenth members; from twelfth homologue only smectic phase is shown. The N-I and S-I curves of the series 2 show falling tendency - a characteristic of high melting series^{1,2}. In series 1 the odd-even effect is well marked in N-I and S-I curves, whereas it is absent in series 2. The overall phase transitions of the series 2 are higher than those of series 1. Thus series 2 shows more nematogenic

and less smectogenic characteristics. Only the textures of nematic and smectic phases of series 2 are similar to those of the series 1.

TABLE 2—AVERAGE THERMAL STABILITY (°C) OF HOMOLOGOUS SERIES

Series	N-I	S-N or S-I	Commencement of Sm phase
1	191.2 (O ₄ -O ₆)	114.5 (O ₁₂ -O ₁₄)	O ₄
3 ^a	191.2 (O ₄ -O ₆)	186.0 (O ₁₂ -O ₁₄)	O ₆
4 ^b	126.0 (O ₄ -O ₆)	95.1 (O ₁₂ -O ₁₄)	O ₆
5 ^c	185.8 (O ₈ -O ₆)	189.6 (O ₈ -O ₁₀)	O ₆
6 ^d	188.8 (O ₄ -O ₆)	188.7 (O ₁₀ -O ₁₂)	O ₄
7 ^e	—	104.7 (O ₁₂ -O ₁₄)	O ₇
8 ^f	—	90.8 (O ₁₂ -O ₁₄)	O ₄
9 ^g	191.2 (O ₄ -O ₄)	121.2 (O ₁₂ -O ₁₂)	O ₄

^aRef. 4. ^bRef. 14. ^cRef. 15. ^dRef. 16. ^eRef. 17. ^fRef. 18. ^gRef. 19.

Table 2 shows the average thermal stabilities and stage of commencement of the smectic phase for the following homologous series selected for comparative study: *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-n-alkoxy-cinnamates (1), *p*-nitrophenyl *p*'-n-alkoxycinnamates⁴ (3), *p*-methoxyphenyl *p*'-n-alkoxycinnamates¹⁴ (4), *p*-(*p*'-n-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)acetophenones¹⁵ (5), methyl *p*-(*p*'-n-alkoxycinnamoyloxy)benzoates¹⁶ (6), *p*-chlorophenyl *p*'-n-alkoxybenzoates¹⁷ (7), *p*-n-alkoxybenzylidene *p*'-chloroanilines¹⁸ (8) and *p*-bromophenyl *p*'-n-alkoxycinnamates¹⁹. The general structure of these series taken for comparative study can be given as

where, A is CH=CH-COO for 1, 3, 4, 5, 6 and 9, COO for series 7 and CH=N for series 8; B is Cl for series 1, 7 and 8, Br for series 9, NO₂ for series 3, OCH₃ for series 4, COCH₃ for series 5 and COOCH₃ for series 6. Most of the molecular geometry of all the homologous series under comparison is common; the only uncommon part being the different terminal groups at one end or different central linkages in them. The reason for the variations seen in the average thermal stabilities and the commencement of the smectic mesophase can be looked upon due to the differences in the molecular geometry of these series and the molecular forces arising therefrom. The N-I stabilities for series 1, 3 and 9 are lowest and equal which may be due to their less terminal attractions. The series 4, 5 and 6 have higher N-I stabilities due to their terminal polar and longer groups. But NO₂ group is also polar, and therefore the N-I stability for the series 3 should have been higher too. Yet, this is not the case. It should be mentioned here that series 3 has also higher S-N or S-I stability which in fact is

somewhat in contravention to the normally accepted generalisation regarding the NO₂ group²⁰. The absence of enantiotropic nematic phase in the case of series 7 and 8 may be due to the tilting effect of C-Cl dipole²¹. Series 1 and 9 with polarisable Cl and Br groups and longer -CH=CHCOO- linkage speak for their high S-N or S-I stability; the Br group is broader than Cl group, therefore the S-N or S-I stability of series 9 is more than that of series 1. For the same reasons, the S-I stability of the series 5 and 6 are more²². The lower S-N or S-I stability of the series 4 is due to its terminal polar group. Though -COO- linkage is more non-coplanar than -CH=N- linkage, the S-I stability of series 7 is more than that of series 8, which is a surprising fact. Similarly, the early commencement of the smectic mesophase in a homologous series is because of the more lateral attractions of the molecules at a lower homologue; the late commencement of the smectic phase in a series speaks for its higher ratio of terminal-to-lateral attractions.

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